

Study of molecular interaction in ternary liquid systems by ultrasonic technique

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Abstract : Density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K were reported for the ternary mixtures of methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether + 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol. From the experimental data, acoustical parameters such as adiabatic compressibility (β), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f), internal pressure (π_i) and their excess values have been calculated. The observed trends and variation of these parameters helps in understanding the intermolecular interactions between the component molecules in the mixture and are discussed in terms of variation of composition, chainlength of alcohols. The results are interpreted in the light of molecular association to the hydrogen bonding.

Keywords : Ternary mixtures, excess values, molecular interaction, acoustical parameters, alkanols.

Introduction

Ultrasonic waves with low amplitude have been used by many scientists to investigate the nature of molecular interaction in binary, ternary and quaternary liquid mixtures. Ultrasonic measurements are extensively used to study molecular interactions in pure liquid and liquid mixtures¹.

The degree of self association in 1-alcohols decreases as the carbon chain length in the molecule increases. The objective of the present investigation is to determine the density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of the ternary systems formed from the oxygenated compounds such as diisopropyl ether and alcohols, as well as methylcyclohexane. From the measured values of ultrasonic velocity, density and viscosity thermodynamic parameters β , L_f , V_f , π_i and excess parameters β^E , L_f^E , V_f^E , π_i^E have been calculated. The interaction between the components of the mixtures is investigated in terms of these excess parameters.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent (A.R.) and spectroscopic reagent (S.R.) grades. The speed of sound waves were obtained by using ultrasonic interfe-

rometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at a fixed frequency of 3 MHz with an accuracy of $\pm 2 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. An electronically digital operated constant temperature bath (RAAGA Industries, Chennai) has been used to circulate water through the double walled measuring cell made up of steel containing the experimental solution at the desired temperature. The density of pure liquids and liquid mixtures were determined using a pycnometer by relative measurement method with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ K}$ (Model : Shimadzu AX-200). The pycnometer was calibrated at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K with double distilled water and gave an estimated reproducibility of $\pm 0.0001 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. An Ostwald's viscometer which is 10 mL capacity was used for the viscosity measurement of pure liquids and liquid mixtures. The mole fraction of the second component, methylcyclohexane ($x_2 = 0.3$) was kept fixed, while the mole fractions of the remaining two were varied from 0.0 to 0.7 so as to have the mixtures of different composition.

$$\text{The adiabatic compressibility } (\beta_{ad}) = \frac{1}{U^2 \rho}$$

The free length $L_f = k_T \beta^{1/2}$, where k_T is the temperature dependent constant.

The free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (π_i) are

$$\text{given by } V_f = \frac{M_{\text{eff}}U}{\eta k}; \pi_i = bRT \left(\frac{k\eta}{U} \right) \left(\frac{\rho^{2/3}}{M_{\text{eff}}^{7/6}} \right)$$

where b is a constant which takes 2 for cubic packing, R the gas constant and T is the temperature in K.

The excess parameters (A^E) = $A_{\text{exp}} - A_{\text{id}}$

where $\sum_{i=1}^n A_i x_i$, A_i is any acoustical parameters and x_i the mole fraction of the liquid components i .

Experimental data of density and ultrasonic velocity at $T = 303.15$ K for pure liquids are compared with the literature values in Table 1 to check the purity of the liquids².

Table 1. Densities (ρ), velocities (U) of pure compounds and comparison with literature data at 303.15 K

Liquids	ρ (kg m ⁻³)		U (ms ⁻¹)	
	Expt.	Lit.	Expt.	Lit.
1-Propanol	796.27	796 ^b	1193.1	1192 ^a
1-Butanol	801.20	802.0 ^b	1229.0	1231 ^c
1-Pentanol	806.14	806.2 ^c	1261.6	1260 ^d
Methylcyclohexane	760.04	765.0 ^{d,g}	1191.6	1209 ^{e,g}
Diisopropyl ether	711.68	711.86 ^{d,g}	972.3	974.9 ^f

^aRoshan Abraham *et al.*, ^bP. Venkatesu and M. V. Prabhakara Rao, ^cS. B. Kalyana Raman *et al.*, ^dJing-Da Ye and Chein-Hsiun Tu, ^eHossein Iloukhani *et al.*, ^fK.V.N. Suresh Reddy *et al.*, ^gThe value corresponds to $T = 298.15$ K.

Table 2. Experimental density, viscosity and velocity values for the three ternary mixtures of diisopropyl ether and methylcyclohexane with 1-alkanols at different temperatures

Mole fraction		ρ (kg m ⁻³)			$\eta \times 10^3$ (Nsm ⁻²)			U (ms ⁻¹)		
X_1	X_3	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
1-Propanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether										
0.0000	0.7003	725.02	716.06	707.09	0.3885	0.3688	0.3475	1033.2	1015.2	993.3
0.2000	0.5001	733.70	729.48	726.60	0.4450	0.4192	0.3958	1066.0	1049.2	1029.4
0.4000	0.3000	750.85	745.16	736.90	0.5688	0.5318	0.4961	1099.6	1089.4	1072.9
0.7000	0.0000	777.63	774.39	768.80	1.0596	0.9671	0.8725	1172.6	1159.2	1138.2
1-Butanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether										
0.3005	0.3997	751.15	739.86	732.73	0.5453	0.5127	0.4800	1097.4	1083.7	1064.4
0.7001	0.0000	784.56	782.60	779.30	1.2452	1.1468	1.0550	1196.6	1184.7	1168.8
1-Pentanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether										
0.3002	0.3999	755.71	750.84	747.91	0.5923	0.5554	0.5206	1112.8	1097.9	1086.0
0.7001	0.0000	791.73	787.76	786.52	1.6038	1.4461	1.3012	1219.8	1206.0	1189.7

Results and discussion

The experimentally measured values of density viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of the ternary liquid mixtures at 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K are given in Table 2. From the measured quantities various parameters like adiabatic compressibility (β_{ad}), free length (L_f), free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (π_i) are reported in Tables 3 and 4. The excess functions β_{ad}^E , L_f^E , V_f^E and π_i^E of all the three ternary systems at 303.15 K are summarized in the Figs. 1-4.

From Table 2, it is observed that in all the three systems the density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity of the ternary mixtures are increasing with increasing mole fractions of 1-alcohols. The increase in velocity, density and viscosity with increase in concentration suggests increase in cohesive forces due to intermolecular interactions. As the number of hydrocarbon group increase, the sound velocity is found to increase, which is evident from the Table 2.

Adiabatic compressibility exhibits a reverse trend to that of ultrasonic velocity (Table 3). The decrease in adiabatic compressibility with concentration suggests that the interaction between the donor and acceptor is concentration dependent as well as on the hydrophobic character of the aliphatic alcohol³.

Intermolecular free length is found to a predominant factor, which depends upon adiabatic compressibility

Table 3. Adiabatic compressibility (β) and free length (L_f) values for the three ternary mixtures of diisopropyl ether and methylcyclohexane with 1-alkanols at different temperatures

Mole fraction		$\beta \times 10^{10} (\text{pa}^{-1})$			$L_f \times 10^{10} (\text{m})$		
X_1	X_3	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
1-Propanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether							
0.0000	0.7003	12.9206	13.5503	14.3339	0.7172	0.7403	0.7686
0.2000	0.5001	11.9941	12.4529	12.9878	0.6910	0.7097	0.7317
0.4000	0.3000	11.0148	11.3077	11.7889	0.6622	0.6763	0.6971
0.7000	0.0	9.3525	9.6100	10.0404	0.6102	0.6235	0.6433
1-Butanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether							
0.3005	0.3997	11.0546	11.5089	12.0461	0.6634	0.6823	0.7046
0.7001	0.0000	8.9018	9.1042	9.3932	0.5953	0.6068	0.6222
1-Pentanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether							
0.3002	0.3999	10.6859	11.0491	11.3368	0.6522	0.6685	0.6836
0.7001	0.0000	8.4888	8.7279	8.9829	0.5813	0.5942	0.6085

Table 4. Free volume (V_f) and internal pressure (π_i) values for the three ternary mixtures of diisopropyl ether and methylcyclohexane with 1-alkanols at different temperatures

Mole fraction		$V_f \times 10^7 (\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1})$			$\pi_i \times 10^{-6} (\text{pa})$		
X_1	X_3	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
1-Propanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether							
0.0000	0.7003	4.9705	5.2343	5.5386	236.5	234.3	231.7
0.2000	0.5001	3.7292	3.9885	4.2187	278.0	275.0	273.8
0.4000	0.3000	2.3433	2.5561	2.7727	351.2	345.0	338.7
0.7000	0.0	0.7954	0.8966	1.0179	574.3	559.4	542.3
1-Butanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether							
0.3005	0.3997	2.8708	3.0902	3.3205	308.1	302.5	298.2
0.7001	0.0000	0.7805	0.8689	0.9661	533.6	522.3	511.1
1-Pentanol + methylcyclohexane + diisopropyl ether							
0.3002	0.3999	2.7689	2.9881	3.2393	303.9	299.9	295.9
0.7001	0.0000	0.6520	0.7486	0.8594	528.3	511.2	495.6

Fig. 1. Variation of excess adiabatic compressibility (β^E) with mole fraction of diisopropyl ether + methylcyclohexane + 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol at 303.15 K.

Fig. 2. Variation of excess free length (L_f^E) with mole fraction of diisopropyl ether + methylcyclohexane + 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol at 303.15 K.

and shows a similar behavior as that of compressibility (Table 3). According to model proposed by Eyring and

Kinkaid⁴, ultrasonic velocity should decrease with increase in free length and vice versa. This is also in accordance

Fig. 3. Variation of excess free volume (V_f^E) with mole fraction of diisopropyl ether + methylcyclohexane + 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol at 303.15 K.

Fig. 4. Variation of excess internal pressure (π_i^E) with mole fraction of diisopropyl ether + methylcyclohexane + 1-propanol, 1-butanol and 1-pentanol at 303.15 K.

with the expected increase in compressibility following a decrease in ultrasonic velocity in these mixtures. The observed decrease in β and L_f indicates that hydrogen bonding between unlike molecules dominates over that of dissociation effect⁵. Increase of β and L_f with temperature for all the system suggests breaking of hetero- and homo-association of molecules at higher temperature. The addition of 1-ols with mixture leads to a compact structure due to the presence of dipolar interaction. This contributes to a decrease in free length and hence compressibility. The regular fall in free length with the mole fraction of alkanols may be attributed to the close approach of the molecules⁶. The present trend is in accordance with the findings of Nikam *et al.*⁷. According to which the regular fall in free length causes a rise in ultrasonic velocity. This is accordance with the expected decrease in adiabatic compressibility following an increase in the ultrasonic velocity in all the ternary systems. However, the increase in temperature makes the free length to in-

crease due to the thermal expansion of liquids⁸. Table 4 shows that, as the concentration of alcohols increases, free volume decreases whereas the internal pressure increases. Such an increase in internal pressure generally indicates association through hydrogen bonding⁹. This suggests that the close packing of the molecule inside the shield, which may be brought about by the increasing magnitude of interaction¹⁰.

Though alkanols are self associated liquids, they can form hydrogen bonding with non-self associated liquid diisopropyl ether. Such a type of interaction has been reported by Elena *et al.*¹¹ in the mixtures of alkanols + diisopropyl ether or dibutyl ether.

In order to substantiate the presence of interaction between the molecules it is essential to study the excess parameters. The deviation of a physical property of the liquid mixtures from the ideal behavior is the measure of the interaction between the molecules, which is attributed to either adhesive or cohesive forces¹¹. This can give an idea about the non-linearity of the system as association or other type of interactions¹².

Fig. 1 shows the variation of excess adiabatic compressibility (β^E) against composition of alcohols in all the ternary systems at 303.15 K. It can be observed that the excess compressibility is negative at lower mole fraction and it become positive at higher mole fraction in 1-propanol and 1-butanol systems whereas from 1-pentanol, it is almost negative in all composition¹³. It is expected that the dispersion forces should make positive contributions to excess values while dipole-dipole, dipole-induced dipole, charge-transfer interaction and hydrogen bonding between unlike components should make negative contributions¹⁴. According to Fort and Moore β^E and L_f^E becomes increasingly positive as the strength of interaction between the components molecules decreases and also the negative excess compressibility has been due to a closed packed molecules while positive excess values are due to weak interaction between unlike molecules¹⁵. The negative excess values of compressibility indicate the formation of hydrogen bond between unlike molecules. The values of excess intermolecular free length L_f^E (Fig. 2) follow the same trend as that of β^E . It exhibits both positive and negative values for 1-propanol and 1-butanol systems, whereas it is negative for 1-pentanol system. The positive and negative deviation of these functions

from rectilinear dependence on composition for the present systems are indicative of interactions between unlike molecules. Large negative values of L_f^E indicate the predominance formation of -OH...O-bonds over the rupture of -OH...OH-hydrogen bonds present in pure alkan-1-ol¹⁶. The values of β^E and L_f^E become more negative with increase of temperature due to weakening of intermolecular forces and thermal dispersion forces.

Variation in excess free volume (V_f^E) versus the composition of alcohols in the ternary systems at 303.15 K is shown in Fig. 3. The values of excess free volume are negative in all the systems. The negative deviation of excess free volume is an indication of the existence of strong interaction between the components¹⁷. This confirms the strong hydrogen bonding between ether and alcohol molecules. The negative excess internal pressure (π_1^E) over the entire range of mole fraction of the systems (Fig. 4) also supports the present conclusion and clearly shows that the existing interactions are strong and are dipole-dipole type. The negative π_1^E decreases with increase in chain length of alkanols indicating the interaction is greater in 1-pentanol compared to other alkanols.

Conclusion :

The increase in ultrasonic velocity indicates association among the molecules of a solution. The association between the molecules leads to a compact structure, which in turn produces a decrease in compressibility due to dipole-dipole interaction. The variation of acoustical parameters and magnitude of the excess functions suggest that the molecular interaction in the ternary mixture is due to the dominance of hydrogen bonding through polar oxygen atom of diisopropyl ether and hydrogen atom of alcohols and the order of interaction is 1-pentanol > 1-butanol > 1-propanol. The strength of interaction tends to be weaker with an increase in temperature, which may be due to presence of weak intermolecular forces and thermal dissociation of hetero aggregates in liquid mixtures.

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